

DOI:

Verbal representation of notions in animated discourse: thematic groups

Veselovska I. V., Student,

Borys Grinchenko Kyiv University

Gryshchenko O. V., Scientific supervisor, PhD (Linguistics), Associate professor, Language and Communication Department,

Borys Grinchenko Kyiv University

This paper deals with verbal representation of notions in animated discourse, particularly with the lexeme SOUL in the animated film «Soul». Despite the fact that animated cartoons are entertaining, and worldwide appreciated, studies have demonstrated that they are not neutral, but multifaceted and are likely to convey deep messages to both young viewers and adults. That is why the research on the verbalization of SOUL in animated discourse is of great interest. The subject of the study is the analysis of linguistic means for symbolic representation of SOUL through the conversations, venues, dreams, and social interactions of the main characters in the animated film discourse.

Animated film discourse usually has a great appeal to an audience of different age groups. For children animated films are considered to be a means of entertainment, adults can find the reflection on their problems and even detect ways of dealing with them. So, animated film discourse can be seen as an integral part of children's discourse. Children's discourse, in contrast to the discourse of adults, has its own characteristics, especially from the aspect of language means. We pay attention particularly to discourse continuity, to the idea that sentences in close succession are more likely to be related to the same topic. Continuity of children's discourse can help to provide the connection that holds together noisy social cues into a coherent referential structure, allowing children to aggregate information about what words mean across multiple utterances in simple and grounded contexts (Alexandra C. Horowitz, Michael C. Frank 2013).

Children begin to be puzzled and curious about things that are usually vague even for grown-ups. In this regard, animated film discourse can help children not only to enrich their vocabulary, promote the formation of coherent speech and correct grammatical structures, but also to explain crucial issues of human lives with the help of linguistic and cinematographic means.

Investigating verbal means for representing the lexeme SOUL, we have chosen the material in a form of the computer-animated film «Soul» produced by Pixar Animation Studios for Walt Disney Pictures. The computer-animated film was directed by Pete Docter and co-directed by Kemp Powers and released in 2020.

As for the filmmakers at Pixar, while creating the animated film characters and the scenario, they first needed to figure out how to portray souls themselves. There was a lot of scrupulous research done for it, and

director Pete Docter noticed that people see souls as formless and non-physical air. The moviemakers explored all sorts of research, even becoming captured by the science of aerogel, the lightest solid material on Earth, which is widely used in the aerospace industry.

The title of the computer-animated film under analysis gives us a deep understanding of the main idea and message. «Soul» shows up as an emotional consequence after a wearisome trip between two dimensions and due to the fact that children’s perspective is subtle and immature, there is a necessity for simple, understandable, and not ambiguous verbal means.

That’s why we sorted the list of selected lexical items into 5 main groups: Characters, Places, Birth, Music, and Dreaming. Later we formulated subgroups for the group Characters into Hypothetical, Real, and Two-dimensional; for the group Places into Terrestrial and Celestial; for the group Birth into Adjectives, Nouns and Phrases to clarify the essence of examples, pieces of the utterance of the heroes that were taken from animated discourse in a computer-animated film «Soul» (see Table 1).

SOUL’S LEXICAL ITEMS	Characters	Hypothetical	Real	Two-dimensional
		New souls (soul orbs); Lost souls; 22; the Jerrys – ethereal beings; Terry	Dez (barber and professional listener); Dorothea Williams; Curley Baker;	Joe Gardner; Mr. Mittens (therapy cat); Moonwind Stardancer Mystics Without Borders (Windstar Dreamermoon, Dancerstar Windmoon, Dreamerwind Dreamerdreamer);
	Places	Terrestrial		Celestial
		New York, The Half Note Barbershop,		The Great Before, The Astral Plane, Personality Pavilions, The Hall of Everything, You Seminar, the Zone, the Earth Portal, the Great Beyond
	Birth	Adjectives	Nouns	Phrases
		excitable unique individual enthused marvelous	rebranding matching mentoring illusion gift spark	starting point hypothetical another chance fill out your pass the body is in a holding pattern

		purpose mission	be in for a treat to get turned around
Music	Jazz, fell in love with jazz, to be lost in the music, jump into the music, get the gig, land the gig of life, stick with it. The music is just an excuse to bring out the YOU.		
Dreaming	to go into the zone (zone out), the Fish Tale, to have compassion, to beat someone's dream, spark, to be in a trance, purpose and passion, reverence, contributions, challenge, an obsession – insane, to be disconnected from life. To be happy as a clam. A selection of moments from your own inspiring life!		

Table 1. Thematic groups.

Due to the fact that such subgroups as Music and Dreaming are specified more with the use of citation, phrases, and clichés, we decided to analyze them through content and contextual analysis. Because the phrases separately have one ordinary and understandable meaning, but in the context of the computer-animated film they obtain one more hidden, symbolic meaning. For example, in The Fish Tale from the group Dreaming, we are not able to grasp the meaning of the phrase without further clarification, and more profound analysis. The main hero Joe Gardner in the endless chase for the dream of his life came to a dead end and needed some help, and another character Dorothea Williams told him a story about a fish searching for the ocean:

«I heard this story about a fish who swims up to another older fish and says...

Young Fish: I'm trying to find this thing they call the ocean.

Old Fish: The ocean? That's what you're in right now.

Young Fish: This? This is water. What I want is the ocean».

That Fish Tale gave food for thought not only for the main hero but also for viewers, echoing a well-known quote from The Wire with regard to the way that life simply slips past people. Because not being able to see the ocean for the water or the forest for the trees, we will never live a happy life, we have to live right now and enjoy life right now.

While analyzing the main notions in the computer-animated film «Soul» we delved deeper into the key issues raised in the movie, and ways of their verbalizing, that is why further studies of the problem are of great necessity. The study of thematic groups and verbal means in animated discourse may give considerable insight into children's and animated film discourse.